

**Epistemic and Aesthetic Analysis of Imagination:
Its Role in the Creation of Beauty in
Art, Emphasis on Kāśmīr Śaiva Siddhānta**

Ajit V. Katti

Assistant Professor

CMR University, Bengaluru, India.

Email: ajithkatti@gmail.com

Research Supervisor: Dr. B. H. Gujalar

Professor & Chairman, Dept. of Studies in Philosophy
Karnatak University, Dharwad, India.

Abstract: Indian philosophers have concluded that imagination has two distinct categories - mere images borrowed from residual traces of ideas (of memory) and free images. At the time of art creation, intellect ceases to be active to juxtapose all the free images emerging from the consciousness. In the West, there are contrary theories among themselves like some empiricists deny the creative role of imagination in creating beauty in art and idealists distinguish the imagination into two categories one is creative or productive and another is reproductive and the former is free from residual traces or of any determinations. Though scholars have categorized imagination under the creative domain, mere free imagination cannot be the creative cause of the beauty in art. Then what is the role of imagination in creating beauty in art? Utpaladeva discussed the role of imagination in the reflection of self-realization explicitly in *Īśvarapratyabhijñāvimarśinī (IPV)*, by the analysis of these epistemic arguments, this paper aims to enhance the understanding of the self-reflective activity of the imagination in creating beauty in art and examines the singularity among the epistemic and aesthetic concept of imagination of the Kāśmīr Śaivas.

Keywords: Aesthetics, Vikalpa, Imagination, Utpaladeva, Abhinavagupta, Consciousness, Pratyabhijñā, Memory, Pratibha.

Every artist begins the creation of his artwork by imagining its various aspects. Without imagination, there is no creation of artwork or anything that cannot be actualized from thought. Imagination is the beginning of any and every creation, either the creation of the universe, in which we exist or of anything we (human beings) create. In the process of transforming abstract emotions into (primary) art, whether it be music, literature, sculpture, dance, drama, or painting.¹ Artists contemplate the presentation method of images emerging from the consciousness. According to *Abhinavagupta* imagination is a creative process unlike the *Naiyāyika* and the *Buddhists*, it is not only recollecting the past impressions of ideas from memory² but also the creative source of our consciousness. Contemporary Western philosophers and psychologists profoundly believe that imagination is identical to the thought process, but imagination may be something more than mere thought, which is complex. To elucidate precisely the creative aspect of an artist one should have a thorough knowledge of both, artistic presentation and scientific explanation of the artistic presentation. We find references for such kind of singularity in Indian philosophical thoughts, particularly in the philosophy of *Abhinavagupta*.

I have referred to the original texts with translations of *Abhinavagupta* and *Utpaladeva* in this article when comparing them with other Indian schools. I have limited my analysis from Renaissance to contemporary Western thinkers. In Indian schools of thought, aesthetics developed independently. But *Abhinavagupta* contributed to both the fields, viz. Philosophy as well as Aesthetics. I am analyzing the

compatibility between the epistemic and aesthetic notions of the imagination propounded by the different systems of philosophy with the main emphasis on the works of *Abhinavagupta* and *Utpaladeva*.

Epistemic Analysis of Imagination:

In India, the means of knowledge are the same for all systems of thought with some modification. *Naiyāyika*, *Mimāṃsaka*, and *Buddhists* contributed to enhancing extensively the theory of knowledge. But the *Kāśmīr Śaiva* system is the least considered philosophical system by scholars. *Abhinavagupta* was a philosopher, who contributed to every branch of philosophy including Aesthetics. *Abhinavagupta* made an invaluable contribution to Indian aesthetics. He reconciles aesthetic experience with transcendental experience. How other systems of philosophical thoughts enquire about the means of attaining the transcendental state, to evaluate the validity of such means by developing or updating the existing epistemological theories; in *Pratyabhijñā* system, *Utpaladeva* developed and *Abhinavagupta* interpreted the epistemic theory to profound the Ultimate Reality and applied the same theory of knowledge for other branches of philosophy.

Imagination is the significant aspect of the mind, because of imagination we enjoy varieties of artworks like music, drama, literature, etc., for these variations the rites (*Saṃskāra*) are one of the reasons and other mundane conditions affect the choice of the distinguishing art form. According to *Abhinavagupta*, imagination is the starting point of the creation of any artwork. In the epistemic analysis of imagination, specifically the analysis of its origin to development and application in the creation of art. *Utpaladeva* termed imagination as '*vikalpa*', in the *Pratyabhijñā* system *Kāśmīr Śaivas* determined it in both senses, one is perception-cum-cognition, and another is imagination (Cf. *Samvit*). In both senses, the act of imagination is of psychic construction. Further imagination is distinguished into two types of psychic construction (*Vikalpa*), most of which are not unpremeditated since they are inflexible from other psychic events, while some of them are free from the conditioning of previous psychic impressions.³ Evaluating this complex aspect of psychic activity in the light of epistemology is quite difficult, the inclination of this aspect towards metaphysical achievement made it possible for *Utpaladeva* to conclude in his celebrated work *īśvarapratyabhijñākārika*, that, *Vikalpas* are constructed at the abode of intellect (*buddhi*) by the free will of consciousness, which means intellect is a medium to exhibit the images created by the consciousness.⁴

Contemporary analytical philosophers are busy analyzing the actual situation of the universe, and however, the phenomena of imagination are unknowingly missed from their conceptual details. Modern empiricists' notion of imagination, which had the propensity for proposing traditional thought on imagery was refuted on three grounds⁵, the phenomenon of imagination is not dependent on or a trait of images. So, the comparison of imagination with belief was incompatible, because, belief needs something to bear on, in a vacuum or nihilism, it does not find any bearing to hold on. There cannot be any relation of belief with anything that cannot be perceived or known. Hence, the comparison of belief was not compatible with the imagination, imagination has the ability that it can evolve out of nihilism. Nevertheless, after refuting the empiricists' concept of imagination, these contemporary thinkers failed to give precise notions of the imagination⁶.

Imagination, understood by Idealists, after the Kantian period, can be considerable, the interpretations of the notion of imagination are compatible with the no-

tion of *Abhinavagupta's* phenomenal descriptions of imagination in substantial dimensions. Psychoanalysts also accept the notion of free imagination, although they include free imagination in the genus of thought, and conclude imagination goes beyond the notion of belief⁷, which means, it can go beyond the known things, for instance, in the process of analogy, a valid means of knowledge, one can think beyond his knowledge, based on another means of knowledge that is the testimony.

Kant introduced three distinctions in imagination according to the "Transcendental Theory," in which the two are not free, regulated by empirical laws and by a priory, and are reproductive and productive, respectively. But the last according to him is aesthetic imagination, no conditions regulate this kind of imagination, he gives reason for the freeness of aesthetic imagination that, this notion is 'the author of arbitrary forms of possible intuition'⁸. Kant also fails to present an appropriate argument for establishing Aesthetic imagination tends to the category of free imagination, which is free from conditions, as defined earlier, the arbitrary forms of intuition, but the propounded phenomena of intuitions, one is empirical and another is pure, both are conditional. Pure intuition is abstract, and this abstraction is derived from the universality or generalization of past empirical experiences. At last, according to Kant, these pure intuitions are not independent⁹. The association of imagination with intuition also leads to the conclusion that aesthetic imagination cannot be free. This free imagination demands absolute freedom than Kant's notion of being free to create a work of art.

Consider the concept of imagination given by Hegel, who proposes the idealistic theory, in that the Absolute is not pure it is concrete, which means it includes everything that is manifested as existence. He specifically distinguishes imagination from intuition; the latter is the product of attention and self-externalization¹⁰. He declares that the soul is characterized by immediacy, and sensations are part of it, but sensations are different from feelings because feelings are the activity of the subjective mind, and imagination is another activity of the same region, where feelings are active. Imagination according to him is the unifier of ideas that loomed out of Self and is also categorized as creative or productive and reproductive. Finally, we can arrive at a conclusion based on his notions about concepts such as Self, sensations, feelings, and imagination, that imagination is the category of reflection, which belongs to the second phase of theoretical Mind or Spirit. Hence it unifies the ideas that loom out of the soul simultaneously hand in hand with sensations when this process is incorporated with intuition caused by this inclusion self-externalization of the produced idea becomes the aesthetic expression. When the phenomena of imagination is embraced with the activity of the intellect, which becomes the secondary source of the creation, and in the case of intuition, he followed Kant.

There is inconsistency in the epistemological conceptions of the theory of imagination given by the above philosophers. I do not find any consistency in organic relation even within the same systems as well, some of them are contradicting, using different methodologies in propounding each other's epistemological conceptions of imagination be it with aesthetics or metaphysics. Most contemporary thinkers knowingly or unknowingly alienated aesthetics from philosophy, but some thinkers (from non-philosophical backgrounds as well included) inspired by analytical moment limited themselves to the criticism of Arts and philosophical theories of art. Such criticism endorsed collaborative methodologies like socialist

theories in literary criticism, advanced psychological theories, or experiments in the criticism or analysis of performing arts, etc. The Western thinkers limited the phenomena of imagination to the extent of thought, which is the activity of the intellect. But *Utpaladeva* considered the intellect as an inanimate (*Jada*) being.

Naiyāyikas theory of ontology describes the *buddhi* (knowledge), *sukha* (pleasure), *duḥkha* (sorrow), *icca* (will), *dveṣa* (hatred), and *yatna* (effort) as the qualities that acknowledge the soul at the time of their expression and ascribed the quality *bhāvana* to the soul. The theory of knowledge declared that by having the quality of *bhāvana* humans can memorize from the experiences of perception. The above qualities originate from the soul and are the consequences of the functioning of causation. The notion of *Kalpāna* is interpreted and defended as a perceptual state¹¹. *Buddhist* logician *Diñnāga* refuted the association of imagination with sense perception and proposed a counterargument as sense perception is pure, direct contact of objects to the mind. But, as *Naiyāyika* classified perception into two categories i.e., *nirvikalpa pratyakṣa* and *savikalpa pratyakṣa*. B. K. Matilal in his essay pointed them with proper meaning, for *savikalpaka*, 'conception loaded,' and *nirvikalpaka* 'conception free'¹². And *kalpāna* is described and used in the ordinary sense like *kavi-kalpāna*.

Buddhists incorporated the notion of imagination with language, any individual, who expresses the experience of the knowledge of sense perception, then, articulates it through language. While articulating perceptual experiences, imagination adds something more to that expression to clarify what one has experienced. *Buddhists* consider imagination as fictional, which will not lead to attaining true knowledge. Though *Naiyāyikas*, accept the *Buddhists*' proclamation in considering imagination as *pramāṇa*, only in a partial sense and further affirm that it does not produce fictional knowledge every time, sometimes it also manifests the true knowledge, nevertheless, this cannot be considered as *pramāṇa*, because it is not a medium of knowledge to rely on, also it does not have consistency in the context we can expect true knowledge. Hence, both systems considered the imagination as a product of *buddhi* (intellect). As *Naiyāyika* ascribed *kalpāna* to the *kavi-kalpāna*, we could find no explanations about this notion in the discourses of *Naiyāyikas* and *Buddhist*.

Abhinavagupta interpreted *Īśvarapratyabhijñānākārikā* of *Utpaladeva*. *Bharata's Nāṭyaśāstra* (*Abhinavabhārati*) and *Ānandavardhana's Dhvanyāloka* (*Dhvanyālikalocana*) are interpretations of aesthetics treaties and commentary on the treaties respectively. His theories of aesthetics and epistemology are compatible with his notion of Ontology and Metaphysical theories. *Abhinavagupta* reconciled the realist and idealist theories, pluralism, and monism, and proposed a sustainable philosophy. His commentary also exhibited many original thoughts; we can consider his commentaries as independent work.

Earlier we observed some glimpses from the epistemic notions of *Utpaladeva* and *Abhinavagupta*, let us elucidate the same concepts. The philosophy of *Kāśmir Śaivism* developed authentic epistemology which is pragmatic and compatible with all their Ethical observations and Metaphysical attainments. They are thorough realists, unlike *Naiyāyikas* and Concrete Idealists, unlike Hegel, the combination of realistic and idealistic systems made this school stand uniquely than other systems of Indian philosophical thought. The magnum opus of *Abhinavagupta* i.e., *Tantrāloka*, collectively discusses the philosophical facets of the teachings of his several *Gurus*.

In general, every philosophical system in India states that when the Soul is concealed by the corporeal body it ceases to find its true nature, this state of forgetfulness of one's real nature is considered as the person is in a state of ignorance. As we analyzed the three major philosophical systems viz. *Nyāya*, *Mīmāṃsā*, and *Buddhist* consider the notion of imagination as one of the states of being while in ignorance because it is the activity of the *Buddhi*, which is considered as an internal organ manifest and conceals the soul very next from the Ego. But for *Kāśmir Śaivas*, considering the entire manifestation of the corporeal world that emerged out of *Śiva* using his power *Śakti*, then the entire universe is part of the whole i.e., *Śiva*. In the theory of causation according to Buddhists and *Naiyayikas*, the subject and object are two different notions. Hence, their theory of knowledge differentiates between the *pramā* and *pramāṇa*, correct understanding and the means of correct understanding of the objects to the self. In this process, the self understands the precise characteristics of the object but not the object itself. Rather, *Kāśmir Śaivas* considers the means of correct knowledge of an object as self-revealing, in such case, oneself becomes the *pramā* and *pramāṇa*¹³. They accept the momentariness of Buddhists, but this applies to the Soul, which is in ignorance or bondage of *samsāra*, from which they conclude that subjectiveness is momentary when an individual gets rid of ignorance¹⁴ and then realizes Universal Consciousness. Therefore, they considered the momentariness of self and objective entity until one can realize the Ultimate Consciousness.

According to *Utpaladeva*, the intellect is non-sentient, it reflects the forms of objects, in the same way, as it reflects the Consciousness, which is the sentient being, and self-luminous. So, intellect borrows the luminosity of Consciousness and throws light on the objects through which reflects the form of the Object of Perception¹⁵, *Utpaladeva* considers such cognition to be self-revealing as earlier we discussed that *pramā* and *pramāṇa*, here cognition, and the object of cognition (*prameya*) both reveal the Consciousness itself. In such cases, though it is self-revelation, intellect supposes that the sentiency of Self on itself is the state of ignorance. *Abhinavagupta* classifies the states of *vikalpas* into two states: pure and impure in his commentary on *Īśvarapratyabhijñānākārikā* of *Utpaladeva*. Impure *vikalpas* arise when the reflective awareness 'I' presupposes as the knowing subject¹⁶, this reflective awareness (*ahampratyavamarśa*) cognizes reality as the opposite entity, for instance, body, elements of the universe, etc. This impurity is caused by the exclusion of 'non-I,' this exclusion occurs because of the *māya*, the manifested power of the Consciousness itself¹⁷, because of this reason *Utpaladeva* does not consider this as *vikalpa*, but *Abhinavagupta* objects to this opinion, and classifies the *vikalpas* affected by the *māya*, i.e., Ego, awareness of 'I' as impure. Hence, we can easily conclude that the *vikalpas* which are unaffected by the *māya*, the power of the Pure Consciousness, of the Lord, are not residual traces, but creative thought constructions. *Māya* being Ego veils the intellect and leads to the misapprehension that the intellect supposes as it is the sentient and illuminating being. When the veil of the Ego (*māya*) uncovers intellect, then the consciousness within exposes, only *Sādhakas* and *Yogis* attain this extent, this kind of *vikalpas* i.e., without the intervention of the Ego between the Consciousness and intellect, are free from the residual traces, such manifestations have the creative or original ideas. *Abhinavagupta* classifies such *vikalpas* under pure imagination. Hence the conclusion is these pure imaginations are novel in nature. How these imaginations will be

turned into a beautiful art form? This is the current problem, for this, we should shift this analysis to the domain of aesthetics.

Aesthetic Analysis of Imagination:

In creating any art, the artist starts contemplating the subject (*vastu*), which is revealed and when it could be the subject of the artwork, then starts imagining the form for that subject. The artist also develops that form by adding more details, which makes that artifact beautiful. The above is the general process any artist goes through. In this process, artists transform individual feelings (*bhāva*) into essential emotions (*rasa*), which are universal. This transformation occurs throughout the creation of artwork by which the connoisseurs (*rasikas*) experience the beauty embedded in that work of art, this experience is the *rasānubhava*. In this article, I considered the experiential judgments and kept aside the theoretical interpretations because this is not the main area of focus in this article.

Abhinavagupta wrote a commentary on *vṛtti* of *Utpaladeva*, the epistemic concepts he interpreted are compatible with the aesthetic notions of his works like *Abhinavabhāratī* and *Dhvanyālokalocana*, considered the benchmarks of Indian aesthetics. Here I also consider the other philosophical works of *Abhinavagupta* like *Tantrāloka*, and *Parātrimśika Vivaraṇa* in support of making the argument sound and valid. *Abhinavagupta* associates the concept of *Pratibhā* with the thought construction (imagination) that the *Kavi* or in general artists can experience when creating an artwork. Different Aesthetes defined, *Pratibhā* illuminates the thought construction, *Kuntaka* made a difference between the *Śāstra* and *Kāvya* based on their creative methods, the former is purely based on reasoning and the latter is on imagination because *vakratva* in the language of poetic expression will make *Kāvya* extraordinary than *Śāstra* which holds the naturalistic expression of language¹⁸. Epistemology and Aesthetics are the *Śāstras*, the former provides knowledge about the nature of imagination, and the latter, about its application in the artwork.

Few Indian aesthetes recognized the significance of the role of imagination in creating artworks, *Kuntaka* (950-1050 CE) emphasized the power of the imagination of the poet (artist)¹⁹ and acknowledged this as the fascinating characteristic of artistic depiction²⁰, he supported that adornment does not have to be added from the outside, but the artwork itself is the embodiment of the adornment, because of the poetic imagination²¹. The consciousness as a sentient being is infinite in its nature, but the intellect as a non-sentient being limits itself as finite. In normal conditions, laypeople can only be able to extend their thought construction within the limits of residual traces because the intellect can only reflect the ideas from previous cognitions. In the fascinating poetic expression, *Jayaratha* denotes this with the term '*Vicchitti*' in his commentary on *Ruyyaka's* treatises. He defines *Vicchitti* as having an infinite variety and scope, which corresponds to the artistic (poetic) imagination²². *Rajashekhara* (880-920 CE) annotated that *Pratibhā* corresponds with poetic imagination, according to him, the power illuminates the poet within, from which the poet (artist) can perceive things far from his sensual reach. And further, he classifies *Pratibhā* based on two conditions, first as being creative (*kārayitri*) which is subservient to the artist and the second discriminative (*bhāvayitri*) helps the connoisseur²³. As per the epistemic notion of imagination concluded in the earlier section of this article, every luminous *vikalpa* (imagination) emerges from Consciousness and only the few of them will become artistic expressions, what makes these constructions of thought into a work of art?

For this question, the above opinions of aesthetes can be considered as the answer. But there lies inconsistency when compared with creative works which are not artworks, for instance, innovative works of natural sciences, normative sciences, etc., also involve aspects of creative imagination. We should distinguish them from artworks. With a precise understanding of the concept of *Pratibhā*, we can answer the above question.

Through the power of imagination, the existing phenomenal world is created by universal consciousness, a process which resembles the subjective activity of any individual. *Abhinavagupta* draws attention to the locus of the imagery object, i.e., inside as manifestation of a thought construction, as well as the same internally manifested thought reflect through the intellect to have experience of objects from outside. Because of this reason, *Abhinavagupta* and *Utpaladeva* considered imagination as the indulged experience which includes creativity by which individuals can manifest the Ultimate Consciousness²⁴. In the epistemic section, we come to know about the categories of imagination, one is free, and the other is not. The former is independent of the notion of perception; *Abhinavagupta* asserts that imagination unveils and recognizes the individual's *aiśvarya* 'the Real nature of being the Lord Siva'²⁵. The creative imagination is considered by *Abhinavagupta* as the new manifestation of thought with imagining cognition, it is unprecedented (*Apurva*) and concurrent (*Sahaja*)²⁶. This notion of imagination can also be found in his aesthetics. In his commentary on *Dhvanyaloka* 1.6, *Pratibhā apūrvavastunirmānakṣamā prajñā*²⁷, creative imagination (*Pratibhā*), thus is an immediate cognition that can create unprecedented thought. T. N. *Srikantaiya* quotes the definition of *Pratibhā* given by *Bhattatauta* teacher of *Abhinavagupta* 'the creative power of imagination'²⁸. Comparing the notion of imagination in philosophical treaties or aesthetic works in the Kashmir *Śaiva* tradition, we can find a singularity between all the branches of philosophy. This singularity and consistency between both systems cannot be found in any of the Western schools of thought, because of this reason I excluded the Western concept of imagination from this section. Some of the art critics' definitions resemble with what I am considering for the analysis, for example, 'Imagination is involved in any process of learning we can find because imagination is involved in all mental activities'²⁹. But these definitions are made based on the experiences of those critics, which lack epistemic evidence from any system of philosophy to validate them.

In *Abhinavagupta*'s *Parātrīśika Vivaraṇa*, the description of the theory of evolution states that the power of desire (*icca Śakti*) of the *Parama Śiva* is the root cause of the creation of this universe, he created the universe with the help of his *Śakti*³⁰. A similar kind of analogy was used by *Abhinavagupta* in *Īśvara Pratyabhijñā Vimarśini*, here it shows that the processes of imagination of a particular subject is as free as the Universal Consciousness and vice versa. This instance exhibits the thorough maintenance of the singularity of the *Kāśmir Śaiva Darśana*. The concept of *Pratibhā* according to *Bhartrhari* is when the soul is illuminated by the luminosity of Ultimate Consciousness, the heart begins savoring a joy, which does not emerge out of the sensual experience and never fade, digs out deep from within in an infinite variety of newer forms by the Universal Consciousness, in which the subjectivity of an individual enveloped by the luminosity of the Supreme Being³¹. The *Pratibhā* is associated with the *Paśyanti* level of *vac* (speech), which is subtle, eternal, and super sensuous. When the Vedic *Rṣis* realized the nature of reality with an immediate flash of thought, the occurrence of which hap-

pened by the grace of Divine majesty is *Pratibhā*, with this grace *R̥ṣis* articulated the knowledge bought by the immediate flash in the form of Vedas³². *Paśyanti* is one level lower than *Parā vāk*, this resemblance can be found in *Abhinavabhāratī's Rasādhyāya* as *Abhinavagupta* describes the *rasānanda* as the younger brother of *Brahmananda*, i.e., aesthetic experience is one step lower than the Transcendental experience because the aesthetic experience coloured by *vibhāva*, except this remaining experience is same as *Brahmānanda*, in which one can be free from all obstacles, mundane preoccupations³³. Here, *Bhartrhari* points out *Pratibhā's* initial stage, from where an artist gets an insight into the new creation of his artwork, *Abhinavagupta* elucidates the resulting stage, where artist and connoisseur both experience the emergence of *rasānanda*, which is akin to that of *Brahmānanda*.

How, does the relationship between *Śabda* and *Artha* serve in the context of cognition, when this simple notion becomes complex, it can be further classified into different streams such as language and logic, Arts and aesthetics, etc. based on simple notions. In uniting these complex areas, the concept of *Pratibhā* was found to be the connecting thread between them. *Abhinavagupta* relied on such sources to connect the areas of assertion and meaning, from *Bhartrhari's Vākyapadiya* and *Utpaladeva's Īśvarapratyabhijñākārika*³⁴. *Mahimabhata*, the successor of *Abhinavagupta* defines the concept of *Pratibhā*, the thought process of a *Kavi*, which is concentrated on the *śabda* and *artha* (sense and reference) pertinent to the *rasas* is *Pratibhā*. *Mahimabhata's* expression '*svrupasparśa*' is remarkably close to the *Trika* philosophy³⁵, he associates this actuation with the moment of emergence of the *Pratibhā*³⁶.

The concept of *Pratibhā* was developed in various aspects by *Abhinavagupta* in his *Tantrāloka*. He considers this to be the concept of *Samvit*, consciousness, or *Parā vāk*³⁷. His aesthetic theory of *rasa* also refers to the experience of it in the genus of *Samvit*. A marvel of the genius of *Abhinavagupta* shines in all his works, either independent or interpretations of others' works maintaining the singularity in exhibiting *Kāśmir Śaiva* philosophy without giving any place for the contradicting conceptualizations.

It clears here, how *Abhinavagupta* identified the *parā*, transcendent or supreme Goddess with the notions of *Pratibhā* and *camatkṛti*. *Pratibhā* is the root cause of mystical experience and aesthetic insight, which is implicit in the connotation of illuminating insight³⁸ exposed to the elements of language and reality. This experience demands concentrated contemplation, *Abhinavagupta* held a view on poetic creation that occurs after the completion of experience and contemplated it. The corresponding reference for *Abhinavagupta's* view can be found in the *śukranītisāra*, which remarks on the introductory conduct of the Indian imager: "He is to be expert in contemplative vision (*yoga-dhyāna*), for which the canonical perceptions provide the basis, and only in the way, and not by direct observation, are the required result to be attained." (Fundamentals of Indian Art by A. K. Coomaraswamy. P. 59). Whenever an artist starts contemplating the subject matter to create an artwork, imagination is the only key to opening the doors to find the precise forms and contents, then at the level of concentrated imagination, by the grace of illuminating insight i.e., *Pratibhā*, that artist can precisely assume the detailing of an artwork. The metaphor used to denote the *Pratibhājñāna*, which is immediate and all-embracing insight as *Śikharasthajñāna*, can be said to be a bird eye view. *Tantrāloka* often mentioned how the grace of the Goddess on those who are

engaged in imagining one-pointedly illustrated in the verse as follows,

*Ādyodrekamahatvepi pratibhātmani niṣṭhitah||78||
Dhryam kavivavakṛtvaśālitām yānti sarvataḥ*³⁹

This concentrated reflection of imagining within unfolds the genius, being within as the aspect of the *Samvit* i.e., the Consciousness will certainly attain the ability in poetic creation and oratory gifts⁴⁰.

Kuntaka describes the imaginative turn and ideas that lead to the *vakratva* or *vakrabhava* which is the extraordinariness of distinct poetic expression⁴¹, such expressions will not be found in logical expressions.

Indian philosophical systems from the Vedic period identified the concept of *Rasa* with the Self (*Atman*). *Taittiriya Upanishad* describes the nature of the Self deploys the term '*rasa*.' *Raso vai saḥ rasam hevyāyam labdhavā*.... The same is maintained till now, except *rasa* other elements of artistic expression viz. *vibhāva*, *anubhāva*, etc. belong to the mundane experiences, but *rasa* only belongs to the experience of the transcendental domain. As discussed earlier, the *rasa* experience is one step below the experience of Brahman. In the former context the connoisseur while being involved in the experience of any artwork, temporarily transcends the limitation of time and space, but in the latter case, the *Yogi* or the *Sādhaka* permanently transcends the limitation of time and space. Because of this transcendental nature, nevertheless, it is temporary, and that too makes us experience the blissfulness of Consciousness. Therefore, *rasa* is considered the nature of the Soul. According to *Abhinavagupta*, aesthetic enjoyment is experienced by the Consciousness itself. So, when an artist starts imagining while initiating the work of art, imageries start evolving out of Consciousness. From the above arguments, it is known that the domain of *Rasa*, the source of *Pratibhā* and *vikalpas* or imagination is the same i.e., the Consciousness or Soul. The starting point and the ending point of the aesthetic experience are the same. When an artist thinks of creating an artwork it indicates the desire of *Śiva*, *Icca Śakti*, before the creation of this universe. The artist's concentrated contemplation is identical to *Jñāna Śakti*. Exhibition of created artwork for the enjoyment of connoisseurs, both stand for the *Kriya Śakti* of *Śiva*. In another way, it can be articulated as, the whole creation evolved out of *Śiva* with the help of his *Śakti*, and the artist's creation evolved out of his Consciousness, which is identical with *Śiva*, with the help of *Pratibhā* identical with the *Śakti*. This singularity in the doctrines of epistemology, aesthetics, and metaphysics discloses to the world the wisdom of *Abhinavagupta*.

Conclusion

Of all the above arguments analyzed in this article in the two sections, one epistemic analysis, and the other aesthetic analysis, to trace the role of imagination in creating beauty in art. I first analyzed the notion of imagination concerning epistemology, from the Renaissance to the contemporary period was considered the main school of Western Philosophical Thought. Inconsistency and non-singularity between the notions of imagination and emotion are found in every school of thought, the same problem is found in some Indian philosophical systems. Because of these reasons, do not consider the theory of these schools in Aesthetic analysis, however, the Indian Schools of thought are an exception to this, aesthetic theory developed independently of these schools in India.

The Comparison of the epistemic theory of *Pratyabhijña Darśana* and the aesthetic theory of *Abhinavagupta* leads to the conclusion that any new creation starts with imagination, whether the creation of the universe or an artwork. But

how does this mere imagination beautify the artwork? Other than artwork, doctrines of natural sciences or social sciences also create new knowledge in their development, but they are not considered works of beauty, only artworks are considered work of beauty. The reason for this, as already concluded in the earlier section of this article, *Pratibhā* makes the imagination juxtapose its thought construction using threads of *rasas*.

When an artist deeply contemplates about to create artwork, this deep contemplation is nothing but concentrated imagination, when the concentration level increase *Pratibhā* takes over the imagination and embraces it with *rasa*. The *Pratibhā* is the notion which incorporates the imagination with *rasa*. Consciousness is the locus of these three notions, which is the source of celestial bliss. This is why whenever any work of art (aesthetic experience), throughout this experience, enjoys the delightful bliss from within, which is the beauty in itself. Hence, the role of Imagination is essential in creating beauty in art, without imagination, we cannot expect the emergence of the *Pratibhā* which gives rise to the notion of *Rasa*. These three are the fundamental aspects of Beauty, but the latter stand behind Imagination.

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Endnotes

1. Timalsina, S. (2013). *Imagining Reality: Image and Visualization in Classical Hinduism. (SERAS) Southeast Review of Asian Studies*. Volume 35 (2013): 50-69. p. 1
2. Ratie, I. (2010). "A five-trunked, four-tusked, elephant is running in the sky" – How Free Is Imagination According to Utpaladeva and Abhinavagupta? AS/EA LXIV.2.2010, S/ 341-385.
3. Ratie, I. (2010). "A five-trunked, four-tusked, elephant is running in the sky" – How Free Is Imagination According to Utpaladeva and Abhinavagupta? AS/EA LXIV.2.2010, S/ 341-385. P. 342.
4. *Sānaisargika evāsti vikalpe savairacchāriṇi| yatabhimatasamsthānābhāsanād budhigocare|| Īśvarapratyabhijñākārika* 1,6,10.
5. Scruton, R. (2002). *Art and Imagination: A study in the Philosophy of Mind*. P 93.
6. Ibid.
7. Scruton, R. (2002). *Art and Imagination: A study in the Philosophy of Mind*. P 97.
8. Pandey, K. C. (1991). *Comparative aesthetics vol.2*. p.325
9. Pandey, K. C. (1991). *Comparative aesthetics vol.2*. p. 300
10. Pandey, K. C. (1991). *Comparative aesthetics vol.2*. p. 386
11. Berger, D. (2014). *The role of imagination in perception*. The Indian Philosophy Blog. (17/05/2014).
12. Matilal, B. K. (1986). *Perception: An Essay on Classical Indian Theories of Knowledge*. p.313.
13. Chapter – 3 इदमेतादृगित्येवं यद्वशाब्दयवतिष्ठते वस्तुप्रमाणं तत्सोऽपि स्वाभासोऽभिनवोदयः॥१॥ सोऽन्तस्थाविमर्शात्मा देशकालाद्यभेदिनि। एकाभिधानविषये मितिर्वस्तुन्यभाधिता॥२॥ Trans. By B. N. Pandit p. 121-122.
14. In Kāśmīr Śaivism, they consider that when an individual gets initiated by Guru then the personal ignorance gets eliminated, which is limited to intellectual ignorance, one should get eliminated from the ignorance which concealed the soul there has been prescribed four means (upāyās). Singh, J., & Maheshvarananda, S. (Eds. & Trans.). (2008). *Śri Tantrāloka Vol. 1*. p. 12.
15. Torella, R. (1994). *Īśvarapratyabhijñākārika of Utpaladeva with the author's vṛtti*:

- Critical edition and annotated translation.* P. 94.
16. Torella, R. (1994). *Īśvarapratyabhijñākārika of Utpaladeva with the author's vṛtti: Critical edition and annotated translation.* P. 131-132. Verse I.6.4-5.
17. Ibid
18. De, S. K. (2002). *Sanskrit Poetics as a study of Aesthetics.* P. 35
19. In this article the concepts or principles are analyzed keeping in mind that which should be universal and applicable to every classical art. Therefore, the reference to some specific art form changed into general connotations. Example: Poet as Artist.
20. De, S. K. (2002). *Sanskrit Poetics as a study of Aesthetics.* P. 35
21. De, S. K. (2002). *Sanskrit Poetics as a study of Aesthetics.* P. 36
22. De, S. K. (2002). *Sanskrit Poetics as a study of Aesthetics.* P. 37
23. De, S. K. (2002). *Sanskrit Poetics as a study of Aesthetics.* P. 39
24. Ratie, I. (2010). "A five-trunked, four-tusked, elephant is running in the sky" – How Free Is Imagination According to Utpaladeva and Abhinavagupta? AS/EA LXIV.2.2010, S/ 341-385. P. 346.
25. Ratie, I. (2010). "A five-trunked, four-tusked, elephant is running in the sky" – How Free Is Imagination According to Utpaladeva and Abhinavagupta? AS/EA LXIV.2.2010, S/ 341-385. P. 348.
26. Ratie, I. (2010). "A five-trunked, four-tusked, elephant is running in the sky" – How Free Is Imagination According to Utpaladeva and Abhinavagupta? AS/EA LXIV.2.2010, S/ 341-385. P. 359.
27. Krishnamoorthy, K. (Ed. & Trans.). (1997). *Dhvanyalokalocana of Abhinavagupta with an anonymous Sanskrit commentary.* P. 42.
28. Raghavan, V. & Nagendra (Eds.). (1996). *An Introduction to Indian Poetics.* P. 63.
29. Walton, K. L. (1990). *Imagining and knowing: The shape of fiction.* Oxford University Press. p. 16. In the same we can see another reference, Mc Ginn (2004: 148) argues that grasp of the meaning requires the exercise of the cognitive imagination – something he distinguishes from the use of mental imagery.' Like independent imagination (Apurva).
30. Mahamahopadhyaya Pandit Mukund Ram Shastri (Ed.) *Para Trimsika with commentary by Abhinavagupta*, (Kashmir Series of Texts and Studies No,18) P. 16.
31. Kaviraj, G. (1989). *Aspects of Indian Thought.* P. 17. (Helaraja in introducing his commentary on the third kanda of Vākyapadiya.)
32. Ibid
33. Gupta, N. A. (2012). *Abhinavagupta's comments on aesthetics in Abhinavabharati and locana.* p. 69
34. Baumer, B. (1994). *Abhinavagupta's hermeneutics of the Absolute Anuttaraprakriya: An interpretation of his Paratrisika Vivarana* P. 132.
35. Ibid.
36. *Yā caiṣā pratisā tattatpadārthakramarūṣitā| Akramānanta cidrūpaḥ pramātā sa marhaśvaraḥ|| - Utpaladeva, Īśvarapratyabhijñākārika |7|* R. Torella referred to intuitive light as the concept of *Pratibhā* in the translation of *īśvarapratyabhijñākārika* (p.136).
37. Baumer, B. (1994). *Abhinavagupta's hermeneutics of the Absolute Anuttaraprakriya: An interpretation of his Paratrisika Vivarana.* P. 133.
38. Ibid.
39. Singh, S., & Maheshvarananda, S. (Eds. & Trans.). (2008). *Śrī Tantrāloka Vol. 4.* P. 79
40. Baumer, B. (1994). *Abhinavagupta's hermeneutics of the Absolute Anuttaraprakriya: An interpretation of his Paratrisika Vivarana.* P. 135.
41. De, S. K. (2002). *Sanskrit Poetics as a study of Aesthetics.* P. 35